

V_m^E for (Methyl Alkanoate + 1-Chloroalkane) at 298.15 K

JUAN ORTEGA*, JUAN A. PEÑA and JOSÉ S. MATOS

Cátedra de Termodinámica y Fisicoquímica de la Escuela Superior de Ingenieros Industriales,
Polytechnic University of Canarias, Las Palmas, Islas Canarias, Spain

Manuscript received 1 June 1987, revised 8 February 1988, accepted 11 April 1988

The excess molar volumes V_m^E have been determined using a vibrating-tube densimeter as a function of mole fraction x at 298.15 K and atmospheric pressure for the twelve mixtures: $xH_{2m+1}C_mCO_2CH_3$ ($m=1,2,3$) + $(1-x)ClC_nH_{2n+1}$ ($n=5,6,7,8$). All these mixtures exhibit a positive V_m^E which increases quasi-regularly with increasing size of the 1-chloroalkane. The results indicate the presence of specific interactions. A qualitative interpretation of the results is presented.

THE object of this work is to contribute new data to the study of mixtures of esters + 1-chloroalkanes, providing at the same time, further information on the structure and behaviour of this type of compounds. Attempts at analysing the behaviour of mixtures of either chloroalkanes or esters with another type of organic compounds are to be found in the literature. We are particularly interested in confirming the considerations made in earlier works on the behaviour of the $-CO-O-$ group of the ester. The effects presented by the interaction of esters with other non-electrolytes, such as n -alkanes^{1,2} and n -alkanols^{3,4} have therefore been studied by means of the results obtained in different thermodynamics functions. The said considerations will be reinforced if additional information of the behaviour of the substances under study with others of different structural characteristics is obtained.

In a previous work⁵, some data were presented on the volumetric behaviour of ethyl esters with 1- ClC_nH_{2n+1} ($n=5,6,7,8$), the behaviour of these mixtures being interpreted mainly on the basis of two effects. The first and clearer is the increase of the V_m^E values with the length of the chain of the 1-chloroalkane, an increase produced almost linearly with the number of $-CH_2-$ groups and which indicates, in part, the contribution of the steric effect of the halogenated hydrocarbon in this type of contracts. However, the second effect, due to the presence of the ester, is attributed to a specific interaction that causes for any one 1-chloroalkane, a decrease in the excess volumes as the number of carbon atoms of the ester increases on either side of the $-CO-O-$ group, as occurs with the behaviour of n -alkanes and n -alkanols.

This work reports on the V_m^E s, at 298.15 K of methyl alkanoates, $C_mH_{2m+1}CO_2CH_3$ ($m=1,2,3$), with alkyl chlorides (from pentyl to octyl), and a discussion of the results is presented, which will help to verify the considerations put forward until now in this and other works.

Experimental

The characteristics of the 1-chloroalkanes employed in this work are identical with those given in an earlier report⁵. The methyl alkanoates were supplied by Fluka and their characteristics, indicated by the manufacturer, were identical in all cases, i.e. purum > 99 mol%. However, both the chloroalkanes and the methyl esters were degassed in vacuum and dried with a molecular sieve (type A4, Fluka). The experimental densities of the methyl esters and those found in the literature are as follows: methyl acetate, 927.07 kg m⁻³ (lit.^{6,7} 927.9); methyl propanoate, 908.15 kg m⁻³ (interpolated⁷ 909.3; calculated⁸ 907.8); methyl butanoate, 892.31 kg m⁻³ (estimated⁸ 892.9).

The excess volumes were determined indirectly from the densities of the pure compounds and their mixtures from equation (1),

$$V_m^E (\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}) = (x_1M_1 + x_2M_2)/\rho - (x_1M_1/\rho_1) - (x_2M_2/\rho_2) \quad (1)$$

The densities, determined with a Anton Paar DMA-55 digital densimeter, present deviations of ± 0.01 kg m⁻³. Before obtaining the values for each mixture, the apparatus was calibrated with double-distilled and degassed water and n -nonane (Fluka) as in earlier works^{9,10}. The maximum error in the determination of the V_m^E for all the systems studied was considered to be less than ± 0.002 cm³ mol⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

The excess molar volumes, calculated at 298.15 K from the densities for the binary systems $\{xH_{2m+1}C_mCO_2CH_3$ ($m=1,2,3$) + $(1-x)ClC_nH_{2n+1}$ ($n=5,6,7,8$)\} were correlated as

$$V_m^E (\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}) = x(1-x)\sum A_i \left[\frac{x}{x+k(1-x)} \right]^i \quad (2)$$

$i=0,1,2,\dots$

The A_1 coefficients, obtained by the least-squares method, are presented in Table 1 together with the standard deviations, $s(V_m^E)$. The curves resulting from each system by using equation (2), are graphically plotted in Fig. 1, where it can be observed that the V_m^E values of all the mixtures are always positive, increasing with the length of the chain of the 1-chloroalkane (the size effect). This increase is characterised by the steric hindrance caused by

Fig. 1. V_m^E at 298.15 K for binary systems (m, n): $xH_{2m+1}C_mCO_2CH_3$ ($m=1,2,3$) + $(1-x)ClC_nH_{2n+1}$ ($n=5, 6,7,8$).

lengthening of the chain of the halogenated hydrocarbon, partially obstructing the interaction between the $-CO-O-$ and $-C-Cl$ polar groups, thus producing ever-greater V_m^E . However, an opposite effect to the above-mentioned one occurs, with the decrease in the V_m^E for any one chloroalkane, as the number of carbon atoms or $-CH_2-$ groups increases in the ester. This negative effect is brought about by lowering in polarity of the methyl esters as any one of the aliphatic radicals joined to the carbonyl group increases (due to an increase in the basic nature of the oxygen of the $C=O$ group). This decrease in polarity implies a decrease in the number of ester-ester contacts and to the contrary, a better interaction between the dipoles of the methyl ester and the 1-chloroalkane.

The functions obtained for each system by means of equation (2) allow the partial excess molar volumes at infinite dilution, $V_{m,i}^{E\infty}$ to be determined for the different component of the mixture. These are given by the slopes of the tangents of the V_m^E vs x curves, when $x \rightarrow 0$ and $x \rightarrow 1$. However, in order to avoid obtaining incorrect values of $V_{m,i}^{E\infty}$ because of the imperfections displayed by curve (2) at extreme molar fractions, the experimental values with $x < 0.15$ were correlated by $V_m^E/x = a_1 + b_1x$, while those with $x > 0.85$ were fitted to a $V_m^E/(1-x) = a_2 + b_2x$ function.

With a view to comparing the values of $V_{m,2}^{E\infty}$ obtained by Dusart *et al.*¹¹ for methyl alkanate + n-heptane mixtures with those found in this work, the partial excess molar volumes at infinite dilution for 1-chloroalkanes vs the number (m) of carbons of the radical joined to the carbonyl group of the ester, $H_{2m+1}C_mCO-O-CH_3$, are plotted in Fig. 2. The values of V_m^E of the methyl alkanate + n-heptane system, as well as that of $V_{m,2}^{E\infty}$ are greater than those of the methyl alkanate + 1-chloroheptane systems, indicating a smaller contribution to the V_m^E of the systems studied in this work, and due to the fact the high polarity of $-Cl$ in the

TABLE 1—COEFFICIENTS A_1 AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS (s) FOR LEAST-SQUARES REPRESENTATIONS OF V_m^E FOR $\{xH_{2m+1}C_mCO_2CH_3 + (1-x)ClC_nH_{2n+1}\}$ AT 298.15 K BY EQUATION (2)

Mixture	K	A_0	A_1	A_2	A_3	$s(V_m^E)$ cm ³ mol ⁻¹
$xH_2CCO_2CH_3 + (1-x)ClC_5H_{11}$	0.521 0	1.848 8	2.572 9	-3.244 9	1.977 0	0.002 2
$+ (1-x)ClC_6H_{13}$	0.382 0	1.482 3	6.286 2	-11.243 9	7.276 4	0.001 8
$+ (1-x)ClC_7H_{15}$	1.340 2	2.554 2	1.499 8	-0.597 0	1.076 6	0.001 5
$+ (1-x)ClC_8H_{17}$	5.098 4	2.749 5	4.113 8	-3.110 4	2.539 7	0.001 4
$xH_2C_2CO_2CH_3 + (1-x)ClC_5H_{11}$	0.040 4	1.217 3	0.360 4	0.000 1	—	0.001 6
$+ (1-x)ClC_6H_{13}$	2.636 0	1.475 5	1.946 1	-4.021 6	2.947 2	0.001 4
$+ (1-x)ClC_7H_{15}$	6.617 4	1.717 5	2.448 7	-4.474 6	3.474 3	0.000 5
$+ (1-x)ClC_8H_{17}$	2.385 0	1.860 5	1.064 9	—	—	0.001 3
$xH_2C_3CO_2CH_3 + (1-x)ClC_5H_{11}$	0.644 4	0.869 1	-0.689 4	3.062 4	-2.294 7	0.002 5
$+ (1-x)ClC_6H_{13}$	0.532 6	0.814 9	1.338 3	-1.702 3	0.948 4	0.000 9
$+ (1-x)ClC_7H_{15}$	2.664 4	1.007 2	1.702 9	-3.042 4	2.232 7	0.000 9
$+ (1-x)ClC_8H_{17}$	0.307 4	1.243 1	1.171 0	-2.595 4	2.154 5	0.000 9

Fig. 2. Excess molar volumes at infinite dilution for $\text{ClC}_n\text{H}_{2n+1}$: (Δ) $n=5$, ($\bullet$) $n=6$, ($\blacksquare$) $n=7$ and ($\square$) $n=8$, in $\text{H}_{2m+1}\text{C}_m\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_3$ ($m=1,2,3$) as a function of m ; ($\circ$) values obtained for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{16}+\text{H}_{2m+1}\text{C}_m\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_3$ (Ref. 11).

hydrocarbon and its greater interaction with the ester cause a decrease in the $V_{m,3}^{E\infty}$. No data of other esters with $m > 3$ are available in order to better compare the values presented in Fig. 2 and, above all, to confirm the anomalous behaviour of methyl butanoate indicated by Dusart *et al.*¹¹ with *n*-heptane, where the $V_{m,3}^{E\infty}$ is situated over the mean curve. Dusart *et al.* explained this unique behaviour

by the formation of an intramolecular quasicycle in the ester, which would originate a decrease in its interaction with the *n*-alkane and, consequently, its excess volume at infinite dilution slightly increasing.

Although the points obtained for each 1-chloroalkane have been joined with broken lines in Fig. 2, it cannot be confirmed that the behaviour of methyl butanoate with 1-chloroalkanes is identical, as it occurs with the methyl butanoate + *n*-heptane system.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Consejeria de Education Gobierno de Canarias for financial support.

References

1. D. D. DESHPANDE and C. S. PRABHU, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, **85**, 1261.
2. J.-P. E. GROLIER, D. BALLEST and A. VIALARD, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1974, **6**, 895.
3. M. LÓPEZ, M. I. PAZ-ANDRADE, J. FERNÁNDEZ, E. RODRIGUEZ-NÚÑEZ and J. ORTEGA, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1987, **19**, 147.
4. J. ORTEGA, M. I. PAZ-ANDRADE, E. RODRIGUEZ-NÚÑEZ and L. ROMANI, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1985, **38**, 1435.
5. J. ORTEGA, J. S. MATOS, M. I. PAZ-ANDRADE and J. FERNÁNDEZ, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1987, **32**, 464.
6. J. H. RIDDICK and W. B. BUNGER, "Organic Solvents", 3rd. ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970.
7. J. TIMMERMANS, "Physico-Chemical Constants of Pure Organic Compounds", Elsevier, New York, 1965, Vol. 2.
8. T. E. DAUBERT and R. P. DANNER, "Data Compilation Tables of Properties of Pure Compounds", A. I. Ch. E., New York, 1985.
9. J. ORTEGA, J. S. MATOS, M. I. PAZ-ANDRADE and E. JIMÉNEZ, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1985, **17**, 1127.
10. J. ORTEGA and J. S. MATOS, *Mater. Chem. Phys.*, 1986, **15**, 415.
11. O. DUSART, C. PIKARSKI, S. PIKARSKI and A. VIALARD, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1976, **73**, 837.